

Rounds

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Rules:

Each player is a Researcher who carries out his academic career, producing data, writing articles, giving conferences and winning projects. As he increases in Fame he will go from PhD to Researcher, Associate Professor and finally Full Professor. The one who reaches the greatest Fame wins!

Each player has their own deck (see symbol on the cards) that must be shuffled at the beginning of the game. You start by taking a University card (which will not change during the game) and 4 cards from your deck. Each turn (except the first, in which you draw 4 cards) you draw 2 cards and play up to 2 cards, except Upgrades. If you have no cards to play, you can skip the turn to draw 2 cards from the Projects deck (contains only project cards and is common).

The points marked on the cards are awarded immediately.

You can keep as many cards in your hand as you want.

Projects (Databases, Experiments and Codes) can be played face down (slipped under the player board with only the name of the card or the score showing) or face up (in the center of the table). If played face down, a card is immediately drawn. Only 1 Article per player can be attached to face down Projects, while 2 can be attached to face up Projects. Fake Projects must always be played face down. If discovered with Reviews, the relative points marked on the card are lost (unless Retraction) and they are eliminated from the game together with the connected Articles.

Articles must be attached to Projects or Metadata and give points to both the player of the card and the player to whom the Project belongs (they can coincide).

Other cards allow you to increase Fame or draw new cards. Pay attention to the prerequisites of each!

The game ends at the end of the 10th round or when at least 1 player reaches Fame = 50 (in this case the round is completed normally).